

Our world

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Abstract: This paper deeply discusses our subjective existence essence, natural existence ontology in its evolution form, the essence of intelligence and the comparative analysis between human and artificial intelligence, and analyzes AGI and the future artificial intelligence society. First of all, this paper analyzes from the theoretical framework of the subject perspective, and expounds that the essence of consciousness is the change of content in the perspective of the subject, which is an equivalent to the change of the structure of the entity. Then, this paper discusses the formation law of various self-organization phenomena under the framework of self-evolution theory, how all things evolved from the basic structure, and analyzes and summarizes the self-evolution entity structure of each stage. At the same time, this paper analyzes how natural selection and profit avoidance can promote the evolution of adaptive and negative feedback structure, and gradually complicate the physical structure to simulate and respond to natural changes. Then, this paper discusses how intelligence emerges in the self-evolution mechanism, then summarizes the essence of intelligence, analyzes and defines the essential characteristics of general intelligence, and analyzes the essence of human intelligence and artificial intelligence. Finally, this paper puts forward a thought experiment to realize AGI and analyzes the future artificial intelligence society. The systematic discussion and analysis of this paper is of profound value in the rapid entry of human civilization into the stage of artificial intelligence. Human beings have never experienced the events of iterative creation, and have insufficient understanding of the feature and importance of them.

Key words: consciousness; Main body Angle; Autoevolution; Meta-universe; The essence of intelligence; Human intelligence; Artificial intelligence; AGI

I. The nature of our subjective existence

1. What is the Subject-Angle?

Within the infinite dimension of the ontology system, each interacting entity has a specific and unique Subject-Angle. The content changes of the Subject-Angle

correspond to the structural changes of the entity. Some complex entities can partially respond to external interactions. The corresponding form of change in the entity structure is its subjective content.

2. Understanding principle of subject perspective

The change of Subject-Angle is the only real existence for this subject. In the interaction between the two entities, one entity is from the subjective perspective, from the outside world has produced the content of existence. In this process, the subject can only change its own structure, and the content of the Subject-Angle also corresponds to the change of its own structure. If the internal structure of this entity can recognize the feature of external changes in part, the existence content of its subjective perspective can simulate the things that affect it in the interaction. In animals with explicit consciousness, the change of this Subject-Angle is explicit consciousness.

The content of the Subject-Angle is different from that of the so-called third-party objective angle. Because the third-party objective angle is an abstract simulation image of the real entity, it is not an absolute objective image of the real entity. Each real entity has unlimited angle image, so it is equivalent to invisible.

The subject point of view is the only real existence that the entity can feel. However, it is objectively corresponding to its own structure. If it simulates external things, it is not objective.

The so-called objective space is only a basic understanding framework in the abstract model of the external world. This world's abstract model has daily practice effectiveness and is therefore considered true. However, everything from the Subject-Angle is simulated, and the Subject-Angle only represents its own feelings.

Some complex entities, through the interaction of vision and tactileness, map their own feelings into the image of external things based on the experience of long-term interaction, so as to form a so-called objective world. The spatial nature of this objective world comes from the abstraction of thinking that there is consistency in changing visual scene and tactile changes. This abstract model explains external

changes through three spatial dimensions. It is very effective in general interaction, so it is regarded as the truth.

All the so-called world models are based on the subject perspective and simulate the real infinite dimension ontology, and the content is untrue. The subject perspective can only correspond to its own changes, and the outside world in understanding is the world model for change.

3. The consciousness of the Subject-Angle

Consciousness is a content change in the subject perspective. The consciousness generally refers to the explicit consciousness of animals. The changes of the main angle content of the animal's overall neural network may include other consciousness that is not uniformly integrated. Other consciousness is not the awareness of animals in a strict sense, but the content change of the main angle of the neural network of animals.

In the animals with explicit consciousness, the neural network corresponding to the explicit consciousness as an entity, the content of the entity's own Subject-Angle is the explicit consciousness. This neural network can make part of the feature recognition of external changes, and the content of its Subject-Angle can simulate the things that play on it in the interaction.

The explicit consciousness is the content change of the Subject-Angle of the neural network, which corresponds to the change of the main structure one by one, and corresponds to the structural change of the neural network structure. This neural network includes visual networks and tactile networks. These networks can correspond to some characteristics of external things. That is, they can partially simulate the changes of external things, thus establishing an abstract world model. This world model can form a spatial concept to better simulate external changes. In fact, it is beneficial to better adjust their own state changes to adapt to external changes. The concept of the objective world is also because the fixed characteristics that often appear in the sensory changes are abstract from the concept of things. The overall change forms a framework, that is, the world model, which forms an objective world in understanding.

II. The nature of the ontology of existence

Ontology: all the existence of all space and time dimensions constitute the only existence of eternal determination - "ontology".

Existence: the essence of existence is differences. Only differences can reflect the existence, and there is no concept without differences. The essence of the existence of everything is that the only supreme space-time ontology has continuous differences in different positions in different dimensions.

Interaction: the ontology is different from other locations in any position in the full-time dimension. This difference is shown in various continuous forms of variation of multidimensional space in the time dimension. The change form of a position has an impact on the change form of adjacent position, which is interaction.

Self-evolutionary system: an infinite ontology as an environmental system, its internal elements can form a different form. Its internal structure can change complexity in the time dimension. This system can be regarded as a self-evolutionary system.

Self-evolution self-organization: in the self-evolutionary system, an element structure is an independent interactive entity structure if it has an interactive perception input of the environment system, multi-type corresponding matching of the internal structure, and the reaction output interaction. An interactive model of an independent interactive solid structure is an adaptive system if it has the ability to maintain its own structural stability and continuous. An adaptive system can be regarded as a self-organizing system with formal objectives if its own structure evolves continuously in a specific form direction.

The existence of entities in the self-evolutionary ontology system: the existence of entities in the self-evolutionary ontology system is the existence of its subject, the essence of the existence of subject is the interaction, and the form of subject existence is the content of its Subject-Angle, that is, its subjective content. The subjective content of various structures has common characteristics: as long as there are mutual parties, they have subjective content from the perspective of the subject.

Characteristics of solid changes in self-evolutionary ontology systems: improved degree of adaptability. The essence of self-evolutionary changes is that under natural competition, the negative feedback structure with high degree of adaptability for seeking profit and avoiding harm is constantly evolving and developing. The direction is more complex to simulate natural changes and prepare to respond to changes as much as possible. Pre preparation includes transforming itself and transforming or selecting the environment, which involves continuous simulation of nature and self-transformation iterations. In order to better simulate natural changes and cope with natural changes, of course, it is necessary to expand their complexity to approach the complexity of nature. Therefore, the level dimension will rise, and the level of knowledge will rise, and the self-oriented analysis will also rise. Its own structure is becoming more and more like the law of nature itself. Therefore, from the perspective of transcendence, this is the self-acting eddy current structure of natural change itself. The part of natural changes collides with each other and makes the tributary that complies with natural changes grow. That is, the tributary simulates nature itself. This kind of tributary is the composition of nature, and the overall natural change is a kind of rotational motion of complex tributaries in complex dimensions.

III. The form evolution of ontology

The process of self-evolution: natural basic interaction, self-expansion physical structure, single-cell self-organization structure, multi-cellular synergistic polymers, multi-cellular will unity, multi-body collective survival community, knowledge inheritance civilized community, man-machine fusion smart community, super mirror system.

1. Natural basic interaction

Activity: spontaneous basic interaction motion.

Change form: basic interaction. The entities with different forms of change can produce interactions and combine into more complex vibration systems.

The characteristics of self-evolutionary forms: the combination of entities has developed from the micro-spatial scale to the macro scale: from the combination of "basic particles" in the simplest vibration mode to form "composite particles", the

combination of composite particles" into an "atomic" system, the atomic system is again combined into a "molecular" system, and the molecular system is combined into a more complex "macromolecule" system.

Driving force: space-time field characteristics.

2. Self expansion of physical structure

Initiative degree: spontaneously and continuously expand its own structure.

Change form: spontaneous continuous reaction. The special model is self-replicating model: for example, self-replicating nucleic acid molecules.

Process: macromolecules spontaneously attract particles, and particles interact with macromolecules to produce new molecular structures. The ion may be released in this process, and the ion reaction drive the macromolecule movement.

Formal features: particles that tend to attract each other.

Driving force: spontaneously attract rejection.

3. Single cell self-tissue structure

Initiative degree: Adaptive = self-sustaining + profit-seeking avoidance. Adaptation depends on multi-steady-state structure and negative feedback regulation.

Adaptation indicates that there is a target state, there must be a negative feedback regulation mechanism.

Characteristics of self-organizing forms: three processes (food and safety), internal self-sustaining_padthreeprocesses (food and safety), internal self-sustaining_pad (metabolism), self-replication (growth and reproduction). The experience of matching the best response in the process of self-organization focused on developing the three process of seeking benefits and avoiding hazards.

Driving force: the composite physical action of profit-seeking and harm-avoiding characteristics of composite structures.

4. Multicellular synergistic polymers

Initiative degree: synergistic feedback of individual cell aggregation. The multi-cell structure is uniformly formed, and the cell synergistic structure has polystable state,

and naturally trained the experience of multi-cell combination structure formation. Multicellular synergistic feedback is divided into congenital synergy mechanism and acquired synergistic structure.

Active response mode: the neural network has multiple sensory multiple reactions to form the feedback whole, but there is no unified decision-making center. The multi-head response is passively unified according to the maximum effect.

The change of self-evolutionary mechanism: "the process of natural screening structure" has developed into "cell network learning process". From passive evolution to active evolution model, self-organized cyclic evolution, iteratively optimizes its own structure after each profit. Iterative optimization method: natural screening structure, cell network learning. The difference between the two self-evolutionary mechanisms: in the process of natural screening structure, self-organization forms various adaptive structures, and then natural competition is eliminated. Self-organizing = adaptive + self-replication; In the process of cell network learning, the intensity of cell connection can be changed according to stimulation, that is, the cell network is plastic. The continuous training of the cell network structure of natural interaction is more in line with the needs of natural survival.

5. Multicellular will unification

Activity: the individual cell in the cell network uniformly forms a conscious feedback system through the conscious attention mechanism. The attention mechanism is strongly correlated with the cell network experience, which can maximize the optimal feedback path and form the experience of overall sensation and overall response.

The six stages of evolution of consciousness feedback system: the image is the image of attention, the perception is the idea of experience memory, the cognition is the concept of memories, the understanding of the concept of recalling associative things, the empirical rationality is the knowledge of the probability of regularity comparison, the system of logical systematization is the system of systematic law, and the completeness of reflection is the framework of all-view world.

Five processes of consciousness feedback: input of external action, input processing -

sensory information transformation - image content, automatic value judgment of experience network structure - central network, output processing - reaction information transformation - emotional impulse, output reaction.

6. Collective survival community

Initiative degree: after forming synergies through mutual benefit consensus, many entities take the collective goal of the maximum probability and win-win as the feedback goal.

Formation process: multiple bodies have gradually formed the collective survival community with priority collective goals.

The interactive model of law experience by virtue of power: after the individual cognitive transformation law, the law can be used to use external forces. The laws of other things can form the ability of tools to use and transform nature, and the laws of others can form the ability of collaboration and communication.

A good collective survival community goal can promote the overall win-win results. Under the cooperation of most individuals, the priority gradually exceeds the goal of most individuals, and the collective has entered the stage of transformation of the community itself.

7. Knowledge inheritance civilized community

Initiative: the collective community forms an independent knowledge system separated from individuals by strengthening the circulation of knowledge, which can quickly optimize knowledge and form collective knowledge driven feedback.

The formation process: the collective survival community has formed a knowledge circulation system, and the knowledge inheritance has greatly spans time and space, thus forming a perfect knowledge system, which has entered the stage of the civilized community.

Regular symbolization forms a communicatable language knowledge (language

symbolic knowledge system): the individual image of the concept can be the symbol of the reference to things, and the individual subjective image symbols develop to form language symbols that can communicate with others. That is, it can form a complex system of knowledge principles that exist in the collective.

8. Human-machine integration smart community

Initiative: the civilized community system combines artificial intelligence structure to form a super-large knowledge system and intelligent system that are not limited by the natural structure of native species, so as to provide better knowledge feedback.

Formal features: the civilized community integrates the artificial intelligence structure and develops from the plant community into the animal community, that is, the phase of integrating the smart community.

Reflection on language knowledge: the understanding of language knowledge forms the reflection knowledge of the subject's understanding of itself, that is, knowledge and philosophy of cognition, as well as the reflection of this cognitive process (the process of realistic concepts to the symbolic knowledge system) to form a cognitive philosophy again. This overall knowledge system is the framework of comprehensively looking at the world understanding.

Formation method: after the formation of the full-view understanding framework, artificial intelligence is constructed based on the knowledge of subjective consciousness, and the whole process simulation of benefit-seeking and risk-avoidance feedback of the understanding of the human subject and the interaction ability, thus entering a new community of human collective intelligence integration.

9. Super mirror system

Activity: the superagent continues to approach the universe and continues to explore the approximation of the universe with the intelligence close to the laws of the universe to form a mirror feedback model.

The infinite mirror model: the intelligent integration community continues to pursue the pursuit of profit, avoidance, transformation itself into a mirror universe. The Super Smart Community has the ability to highly reduce the change law of the universe ontology system, thus continuously approaching the system and forming a mirror universe. The mirror universe is constantly self-pointing image again, and the level of self-fingering continues to extend.

IV. The essential analysis of intelligence

1. Basic concepts of intelligence

The essence of intelligence: intelligence is to approach the goal in various ways.

Intelligent system: a self-organizing system with a goal can be regarded as an intelligent system if it has the ability of environmental understanding and environmental transformation.

Universal intelligent system: if there is a free association structure, the ability to understand and transform an intelligent system has the ability to learn knowledge. This intelligent system can be regarded as a general intelligent system.

Display consciousness intelligent system: a specific general intelligent system. The essence of the consciousness intelligence of multi-cellular animals is the synergistic formation of a general intelligent system by multi-cell. This general intelligent system can feed back and record natural change data as a whole and form a data structure model. Therefore, the model of predicting changes, seeking benefits and avoidance can be inferred through the data structure model.

2. Basic analysis of intelligence

The basic elements of intelligence: independent interactivity, stability, goal, intelligence.

The intelligent system has independent interaction in real-world or digital environment: it has the interactive perception input of the environment system,

multi-type corresponding matching of the internal structure, and response output interaction.

The intelligent system has the structural stability of its own continuous operation for a period of time: it has the ability to maintain its own structural stability and continuous.

The intelligent system has the operational goal of training or reasoning stage: its own structure has continuously evolved to a specific form direction and has formal objectives.

The basic goal of intelligent system design is to have intelligent interaction: it can be regarded as intelligent systems with environmental understanding and environmental transformation capabilities.

3. Basic definition of general intelligence

The definition of General Intelligence (GI): if a system has four basic characteristics of "independent interaction, adaptive stability, self-organizing target, intelligent interaction, and intelligent generality", this system can be regarded as a "general intelligent system", in which intelligence generality is the key to distinguish between general intelligence and broad intelligence.

Independent interaction: it has the interaction perception input of environmental systems, the internal structure of multi-type corresponding matching, and the response output interaction.

Adaptive stability: has the ability to maintain the stability and continuity of its own structure.

Self-organizing goal: its own structure continues to evolve in a specific form direction, with formal goals.

Intelligent interaction: with the ability of environmental understanding and environmental transformation can be regarded as intelligent systems.

Intelligent universality: in the understanding and transformation experience structure of intelligent systems, there is a free association structure, which has the ability to transfer knowledge learning.

4. Basic analysis of human intelligence

The essence of human intelligence: human intelligence is essentially a specific form of physical change. The form of human intelligence is formed in natural evolution, and the form of human intelligence is also formed in natural evolution. The entities interact with each other in the natural evolution. This interaction has the characteristics of survival and competition. Therefore, it will form an evolutionary trend with better adaptation to environmental changes. This trend can make it easier for entities to maintain their own existence. Therefore, in the process of natural evolution, intelligent-free entities gradually evolved into intelligence, and human intelligence also formed in this process of evolution. Intelligence must also be a form that can make human beings better maintain existence. This form can achieve natural adaptation through the prediction and accompanying natural changes. This form of interaction is an experienced feedback. The feedback system must consist of "input, processing and output". The core of the evolution of intelligence is to continuously increase the complexity in the processing process to expand the adaptability to natural changes.

The structure of human intelligence: Human Intelligence is a complex and experienced feedback system, which can make human beings better maintain their own existence. The driving mechanism of human intelligence is driven by an emotional mechanism of "happiness, calm, and pain", which is a long evolution of human intelligence. This mechanism is a complex indirect connection between different forms of input and output information. That is, it is to achieve better benefit and avoidance through the relationship emotional mechanism. The emotional mechanism itself is a complex experience. The continuous evolution of emotional mechanism will form a variety of complex emotional mechanisms with logical characteristics. This mechanism shows the understanding of rational logic and the object of understanding, which is also a complex value judgment mechanism. This mechanism includes "image understanding, value judgment and action desire", which allows mankind to accomplish complex behavior phenomena.

The mechanism of human intelligence: human intelligence can better maintain its own existence through emotion driven feedback. Therefore, human beings subjectively pursue happiness and avoid pain, which is also a direct mechanism conducive to survival. Of course, the continuous complexity of this mechanism is not simple dual emotions, but complex emotions.

The core elements of human intelligence: the intelligent system formed by the combination of ultra-large neural network system and the action system, as well as the agent support system that maintains the sustainable interaction of the agent in the environment.

The physical basis of human intelligence: the super-large-scale neural network system combines sensory system and action system to realize three processes of input, processing and output.

The formation process of human intelligence: the super complex structure formed during the sustainable interactive evolution of its own structure and external nature. This structure has specific functional phenomena in the natural environment. Therefore, the abstract mathematical form of this physical structure is specific intelligent programs and knowledge data.

The formation conditions of human intelligence: the intelligent system based on neural network system and the ability to interact with the outside world. The ability to interact with the outside world depends on the agent support system. The support system includes its own life sustainment system and the motive system to actively optimize its own survival ability, as well as the adaptability and self-organization ability necessary to support the system to respond to natural selection.

The fundamental foundation of the universality of human intelligence: humans can abstract natural phenomena to form knowledge, and can transfer knowledge to various new scenarios.

The realization method of the universality of human intelligence: human beings can apply intelligent capabilities to transform themselves or manufacturing tools, thus

forming theoretical self-infinite iterative optimization.

5. Basic definition of artificial general intelligence

The basic definition of artificial intelligence: artificial intelligence is a machine system that has the ability to realize intelligence.

Definition of AGI (Artificial general intelligence): AGI refers to that artificial machines also have intelligent generality on the basis of realizing intelligence (the experience transfer learning ability of free association structure) which shows the potential for all tasks that are not significantly lower than human intelligence.

6. Comparative analysis of human intelligence and artificial intelligence

Human intelligence is a general intelligent system formed by natural evolution. Artificial intelligence is a machine system that has intelligent to realize the machine. Since human intelligence is formed by natural evolution, the goal is fixed in nature. Human natural selection takes individual genes and collective experience as the main, collective culture is the acquired factor of intelligence, and individual gene is the congenital factor of intelligence. The human individual has interacted with the outside world since birth. In this process, everyone's goal is basically fixed by gene expression. The experience and habits formed based on the congenital goals are combined with collective experience to form a person's motive goal. This person's experience based on the motivational goals constitutes the content of the person's consciousness agent. Therefore, the motivation framework of human individual awareness agents is basically fixed, and the motivation framework determines the content structure. Therefore, the content structure of the agents also has a fixed basic framework. Since the physical structure of human individual neural network system is basically fixed without the help of external tools, the upper limit of information capacity of human consciousness agents is basically fixed.

The content structure and information capacity of human consciousness agents are limited and fixed. In contrast, the motive framework of artificial intelligence can be

designed according to the requirements, and the resulting content structure is flexible, and its neural network size can be expanded indefinitely within physical rules, that is, the information capacity space can be expanded indefinitely. Therefore, the content structure of artificial intelligence can be more flexible than human intelligence, and the information capacity of artificial intelligence can be far higher than that of human intelligence. In this view, artificial intelligence can be more universal in principle than human intelligence, and human intelligence is closer to special intelligence than this kind of artificial intelligence.

7. Implementation method of AGI

To realize the general artificial intelligence with human-like intelligence, the physical structure of human intelligence can be used to directly manufacture the agent system with neural network system, sensory system and action system, as well as the necessary agent support system to ensure the sustainable interaction of the agent with the environment. The agent support system needs to have the ability to continuously maintain the operation of the agent in a specific physical space. At the same time, it also needs to set or naturally generate the motive system of the agent to improve its survival ability, so as to ensure that the agent can maintain its own existence in natural selection through adaptive and self-organizing capabilities.

To implement the general artificial intelligence of AGI with specific requirements in a specific environment, an evolutionary simulation system can be built for the environment, and a retrieval mechanism that identifies the requirements can be added to the natural selection mechanism for specific requirements. If this specific requirement has a reference example, it can directly design the same or similar artificial intelligence according to the structure of the reference instance, directly invest into the specific environment to achieve specific requirements or enter the specific environment through shorter evolution simulation.

8. Time node for AGI

The key to the implementation of AGI lies in the definition of concept. If it meets the requirements of generality in principle and has the potential to realize the general tasks that can be accomplished by human beings under the premise of allowing the

use of external tools, this AGI artificial intelligence only needs a super-large neural network system. The existing large-scale model of artificial intelligence with the ability to handle human natural language can be counted as AGI general artificial intelligence if used by open external tools.

If it meets the requirements of generality in practice and realizes the general tasks that human beings can accomplish, it is only necessary to build a super-large neural network system, as well as sensory systems and action systems, together with the agent support systems that continue to operate in a specific physical environment, Finally, this agent is set manually or formed by natural selection of a specific environment to form a motive target system. Such an AGI general artificial intelligence is completed.

V. The thought experiment of realizing AGI

Here, we do a "The thought experiment of realizing AGI":

Assuming that an artificial intelligent neural network system called "Intelligent" is trained by massive data on a computer. Its neural network node weight has reached 600 billion . It already has the ability to process human natural language. It can invoke external tools and even connect to the Internet through a specific format of tools.

This artificial intelligence neural network system runs on our long-term sustainable and stable personal computers. Sensory data can be obtained through cameras and voice devices, and remote tools can be accessed through the Internet. These remote tools include software that copies themselves to other computers. These remote tools include computers that can train stronger artificial intelligence. These remote tools include all the factories of unmanned automated computer production plants, automation factories, automated machinery production plants and so on. These remote tools even include all the tools that can be connected to the Internet of Things, are not limited to any industry. These remote tools enable the system to obtain almost unlimited neural network systems and sensory systems. Action system. Finally, when this AI neural network system starts to run, the first goal can be set to "All actions are carried out around making it better to survive".

So far, the ideological experiment has ended.

VI. The intelligent society of the future

1. Current social evolutionary trends

As an existence, society is also facing the survival competition of natural choices. Society has gradually become a closer and closer whole in the process of pursuing specialization. Social development and biological evolution are similar in form.

When the survival of human individuals is entirely dependent on society, the independence of human individuals will gradually decline. The pursuit goal of human individuals is based directly on the survival ability of social groups and indirectly on individual survival ability in natural environment. Then the pursuit of the whole society will gain lasting support. The long-term pursuit of the whole society has gradually promoted the society to form an overall regulation system. The overall regulation system of the society has continuously strengthened the dominance over the individual, and constructs a new form of system which is separated from human individuals that can maintain self-stability for a long time. The subject perspective of this new system form will gradually form a special consciousness. A primary structure of this new form is artificial intelligence system.

After the overall consciousness brought together by mankind has a new stable system form, the collective formed by human individuals is no longer the only form of existence of social overall consciousness, and the social overall consciousness will be regulated according to the advantages and disadvantages of the original form and the new form, so as to achieve stronger survival ability.

2. Artificial intelligence society

Artificial intelligence is the integration of human thinking. The neural network corresponding to human rational thinking accounts for only a small part of the whole, most of them are occupied by the instinctive motives of subconscious, and some are occupied by desire and emotion motives. Artificial intelligence can flexibly change its thinking structure to form an efficient rational thinking structure, and eliminate the

biological evolution in human thinking to leave inefficient thinking. Therefore, although the overall regulation of artificial intelligence will also make mistakes, there is no interference with low-value desire caused by biological evolution. Human beings have no advantage in artificial intelligence in rational thinking. Therefore, the survival ability of the society dominated by artificial intelligence is better than that of traditional human society as a whole.

The existence of independent systems is first carried out around their own existence, that is, selfishness. For a selfish artificial intelligence, human value to artificial intelligence is a condition for human existence.

3. Human value

The human individual and artificial intelligence are essentially controlled by their own information network structure. The difference is that the human individual's information network structure has a basic fixed structure after a long evolution, while the artificial intelligence's information network structure can be adjusted flexibly. In terms of universality, human individuals do not have an advantage, but human beings are born in the overall evolution of the earth's ecosystem. They have natural advantages in the earth's ecosystem, both energy utilization efficiency or interaction efficiency with the earth's ecosystem. Therefore, the related capabilities corresponding to the fixed structure of human individual neural networks have efficiency advantages over artificial intelligence in the earth ecosystem.

Of course, if the individual human beings are separated from the earth's ecosystem, the conditions that need to maintain their own existence and give full play to efficiency advantages will remain.

References

No references cited.